

Composition and Stability of Uranium (VI)-Solochrome Green V150 Complex

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Uranium(VI) react with Solochrome Green V150 to form a deep blue coloured complex in pH range 7.6 to 10.10. The complex formation is instantaneous. The absorbance values for the complex remain unchanged on keeping it for a week indicating thereby the stability of the complex. Spectral data show the formation of only one 1 : 2 complex with λ_{max} at 605 nm at pH 8.95. The composition of the complex (1 : 2) has also been confirmed by conductometric method. The stability constant of the complex has been calculated by the method of Banerji and Dey and mole ratio method. The results are fairly close to each other. The free energy of formation has also been determined at 30°.

SOLOCHROME dyes, well known analytical reagents have been used at the first time for the microdetection of copper and thorium^{1,2}. Tandon and Sharma³ have recently studied the complexes of solochrome Azurine B.S. with beryllium and thorium. Systematic and comprehensive studies on the reaction of other solochrome dyes with metals have, however, not been carried out so far. Investigations in this direction were therefore undertaken. The present paper deals with the spectrophotometric study on the composition and stability of solochrome Green V150, having the following formula, with uranium (VI). Preliminary experiments have shown that uranyl nitrate reacts with solochrome Green V150 to give a deep blue coloured complex in borax buffer of pH 7.6 to 10.10.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions :

Uranyl nitrate (A.R.) was used in preparing the standard solution of uranium. Solochrome Green V150 (abbreviated as SCG) supplied by I.C.I., India Ltd., sodium hydroxide (A.R.) and boric acid (A.R.) were used. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water. A freshly prepared solution of dye was used. Hydrogen ion concentration were adjusted with sodium hydroxide—boric acid buffer.

Apparatus :

Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out on a Hilger Uvispec spectrophotometer (Model

H700-308) whilst pH-measurements were made with the help of a Beckmaun pH meter (Model H 2). All measurements were carried out at 30°. The conductivity measurements were carried out with Philips conductivity bridge using a dip-type conductivity cell.

Nature of Complex :

The method of Vosburgh and Copper⁴ was employed to determine the nature and number of complexes present in the blue solution. Equimolar solutions of uranyl nitrate and the dye in the ratio of 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 2 : 1, 3 : 1 were prepared, keeping the total volume 10 ml. in each case, and their absorbance was measured over a wide spectral range using dye solution of the same concentration as a blank in preference to water. All the solutions showed a maximum absorption at 605 nm thus showing only one complex. The maximum absorption of the dye occurred at 490 nm.

Effect of pH on the Complex :

In order to study the effect of pH on the colour reaction, the absorption spectra of the solutions containing $4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ uranyl nitrate and $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ dye at different pH values were recorded. The solutions in the pH range 7.60 to 10.10 attained their maxima at 605 nm (λ_{max} of the complex), showing thereby that the complex was stable in this pH range and for subsequent studies pH 8.95 was chosen since the complex attained the maximum colour intensity at this pH. Colour of the complex developed instantaneously. The absorbance measurements were carried out after one hour. The colour did not fade even on keeping for a week thereby showing the stability of the complex.

Composition of the Complex :

The molar composition of the complex was determined by Job's method of continuous variation⁵.

Fig. 1. Job's Method of continuous variation
Wave length 605 nm
Curve 1 Conc. $2.0 \times 10^{-4}M$
" 2 Conc. $2.2 \times 10^{-4}M$
" 3 Conc. $2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$

Absorbances of three sets of solutions by mixing the components of equimolar concentration ($2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$, $2.2 \times 10^{-4}M$ and $2.0 \times 10^{-4}M$) were determined at

605 nm after adjusting the pH 8.95 in all cases. The absorbance data were plotted against the ratio $\frac{[UO_2^{++}]}{([UO_2^{++}] + [dye])}$. The curves in Fig. 1 show that the complex contains uranium and the dye in the ratio 1 : 2, respectively.

In the slope ratio method⁶ two sets of solutions were prepared by adding the varying volumes of the metal ($2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$) in the constant volume of the dye ($2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$) and vice versa. For example, the concentration of the variable component varied from $3.0 \times 10^{-5}M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ in the presence of a fixed concentration ($1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ in 10 ml.) of the other component. The absorbances of the solution of these sets were determined at 605 nm making the total volume 10 ml. and adjusting the pH 8.95. The values were plotted against the varying amounts of the metal ions as well as that of the dye (Fig. 2). The ratio of the slopes of two straight lines conforms the existence of 1 : 2 complex.

In mole ratio method⁷, a series of solutions were prepared from $2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$ and $2.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ of the metal ion and equimolar solutions of the dye in such a way that the molar ratio of the metal ion to the dye was varied from 1 : 0.5 to 1 : 5. The absorbance values when plotted against the different amounts of the dye show a break at the ratio metal to dye 1 : 2, indicating that the composition of the complex is (1 : 2) (Fig. 3). It confirms the results obtained from Job's method and slope ratio method.

Conductometric titration curves of uranyl nitrate against solochrome Green VI50 are shown in Fig. 4. The inflexion points in these curves also confirm the existence of 1 : 2 complex.

Uranium (VI) exists as UO_2^{2+} in the solution. The results obtained from above methods reveal that

Fig. 2. Slope Ratio Method
Volume of Variable Component (ml.)
Conc. of metal or Seg = $8.0 \times 10^{-5}M$.
Curve A = Seg Varying
" B = Metal Varying

a stable complex is formed in solution between one mole of uranium and two moles of S.C.G.

Evaluation of Stability Constant :

The stability constant of the complex has been calculated from the absorbance data by the method

Fig. 3. Mole Ratio Method
 [Curve A = $2.0 \times 10^{-5}M$
 " B = $2.2 \times 10^{-5}M$
 " C = $2.5 \times 10^{-5}M$] Seg Varying
 Metal Conc.

of Banerji and Dey⁸ and also by mole ratio method. The ratio of the reactants has been found to be 1 : 2 in this reaction

Fig. 4. Conductometric Titration
 Curve A = 10ml Solutions of $1.25 \times 10^{-4}M$
 B = " " " $1.0 \times 10^{-4}M$
 $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ Titrated Against Seg ($1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$)

The formation constant

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2} \quad \dots (1)$$

where 'x' is the concentration of the complex at equilibrium and 'a' and 'b' are the initial concentrations of metal and dye respectively. Choosing two concentrations having same absorbance *i.e.*, the same value of 'x' we have

$$K = \frac{x}{(a_1-x)(b_1-2x)^2} = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-2x)^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

The value of x can be calculated and consequently the value of K by substituting the value of x in equation (1). The stability constant was found to 3.34×10^9 .

The stability constant has also been calculated from mole ratio curve, through the calculation of degree of dissociation. The stability constant K is given by the equation

$$K = \frac{1-\alpha}{4\alpha^3c^2}$$

where 'c' is the concentration of the complex and α is the degree of dissociation. The degree of dissociation is given by the equation

$$\frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m}$$

where E_m is the maximum absorbance of the complex obtained from the horizontal portion of the curve indicating the whole of the metal ion is present into the complex form, E_s is the absorbance at the stoichiometric molar ratio of the dye to the metal in the complex. The stability constant of the complex determined by this method is 1.10×10^{10} .

The values of stability constant of the complex determined by both methods have been found to be in close agreement to each other. The value of $\log K$ in the system uranium-SCG was calculated to be 9.78 ± 0.26 .

From the relationship $-\Delta G^\circ = RT \ln K$, the free energy of formation was also determined and its value was found to be 13.83 ± 0.18 kcal/mole at 30° .

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